

DEVELOPMENT OF A MATHEMATICAL MODEL OF THE MECHANISM OF WATER ACCUMULATION, MOISTURE RETENTION AND WATER RELEASE BY BENTONITE CLAY

Z.F. Pulatova¹, B.T. Sabirov², Kh.L. Pulatov¹

Tashkent institute of chemical technology¹

Jizzakh polytechnic institute²

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Abstract. *One of the most important properties of bentonite clays is their high water retention capacity. Montmorillonite is the main rock-forming aluminosilicate mineral of bentonite clays, with an average content typically ranging from 60 to 70%. Due to its unique layered structure, montmorillonite can swell up to 14–16 times its original volume, while the “swelling–drying” cycle can occur repeatedly without limitation. This property can be utilized for the application of bentonite clays to enhance soil water retention capacity. In this study, a mathematical model describing the mechanism of moisture (water) accumulation by bentonite clay has been developed. The proposed model enables the development of technologies for the preparation and application of bentonite clay into soil, taking into account the properties and structure of bentonite and soil, as well as climatic and weather conditions.*

Keywords: *bentonite clay, mineral, montmorillonite, structure, water, soil, accumulation, mechanism, moisture, water retention, time, water retention model, absorption coefficient.*

Introduction

This paper presents the obtained data on the development of a mathematical model at the field level for water accumulation and release by bentonite in soil, taking into account the chemical–mineralogical composition, structure, and physicochemical properties of major bentonite clay deposits, as well as the rainfed (non-irrigated) conditions of Uzbekistan. In constructing this mathematical model of water accumulation and release by bentonite in soil, methods for developing standard soil water retention curves of the van Genuchten type, standard models of bentonite water retention, and field data on bentonite application were used.

The scientific literature contains a number of studies aimed at investigating the use of bentonite clays for water accumulation and soil improvement in arid regions. For example, J. Mi and other researchers studied the effectiveness of applying bentonite clays at rates of 0–30 t/ha under field conditions over a period of five years. It was found that the optimal application rate was 24 t/ha, at which increases in soil moisture capacity, available water content, crop yield, plant photosynthesis, and water-use efficiency were observed, as well as a significant improvement in soil water retention capacity in semi-arid regions [1].

Long-term field experiments by J. Mi and other researchers demonstrated an increase in millet germination rate, accumulation of dry aboveground biomass, photosynthetic parameters, chlorophyll content, and water-use efficiency, as well as improvements in grain quality indicators (protein, fat, and fiber content). The application of 24 t/ha of bentonite had the greatest effect on plant productivity indicators averaged over five years, as well as on photosynthetic parameters averaged over three years (2013–2015), during which they were measured. An application rate of 18 t/ha had the greatest effect on grain quality. Bentonite, widely distributed in China, is a stable

mineral that requires only a single application and therefore has a clear advantage over synthetic water-absorbing polymers, which degrade within a few years and must be periodically reapplied to maintain their effect [2–5].

Hypothesis and initial data for constructing the mathematical model. It is assumed that, after being applied to the 7–10 cm layer, bentonite functions as an additional internal water reservoir. The total water storage in the root zone of the soil consists of water retained by the soil itself, water accumulated by bentonite, and losses due to evaporation, transpiration, runoff, and deep percolation. As a result of the conducted field studies, it was established that bentonite increases the water-holding capacity and the amount of available water in the 0–40 cm soil layer [10, 11]. In this case, the main initial variables and criteria for the calculation are as follows (table):

Table

Main initial variables and criteria for calculations in developing a field-level mathematical model of water accumulation and release by bentonite in soil

No.	Name of criterion	Criterion symbol	Unit of measurement
1	Time	t	day
2	Depth of the root zone	z_r	m
3	Depth of the bentonite application layer	z_b	m
4	Volumetric soil moisture	$\theta(t)$	m^3/m^3
5	Water storage retained by bentonite	$S_b(t)$	mm
6	Atmospheric precipitation	$P(t)$	mm/day
7	Infiltration into the layer	$I(t)$	mm/day
8	Total evaporation + transpiration	$ET(t)$	mm/day
9	Deep percolation below the roots	$D(t)$	mm/day
10	Surface runoff	$R(t)$	mm/day

Taking into account the initial calculation criteria adopted above, the basic water balance equation for the root zone has the following form:

$$W(t) = 1000 z_r \theta(t) \tag{1}$$

where $W(t)$ is the soil water storage, in mm.

In this case:

$$\frac{dW}{dt} = I(t) - ET(t) - D(t) - R(t) + Q_b(t) \tag{2}$$

where $Q_b(t)$ is the water flux from bentonite into the soil. It should be noted that when $Q_b > 0$, the bentonite releases water, and when $Q_b < 0$, it absorbs water.

This mathematical expression reflects the essence of the cyclic, bidirectional reversible process of “water swelling – dehydration (water release)” in bentonite. In practice, according to this formula, bentonite is recharged (absorbs water) during winter and spring, and partially discharged (releases water) in summer [12–15]. The water storage within the bentonite structure, acting as a reservoir, depends on its capacity volume. The capacity of the bentonite reservoir is expressed by the following formula:

$$0 \leq S_b(t) \leq S_{b,max} \tag{3}$$

In this case, the ratio of the change in water volume:

$$\frac{dS_b}{dt} = A(t) - L(t) \quad (4)$$

Where (t) is the water absorption by bentonite, and $L(t)$ is the release of water from bentonite to the soil and plants. In this case, water absorption is expressed by the following formula:

$$A(t) = k_a I_b(t) \left(1 - \frac{S_b}{S_{b,\max}} \right) \quad (5)$$

Where k_a is the absorption coefficient (0–1), and $I(t)$ is the portion of infiltration that actually reaches the layer with granules. According to research findings, the greater the available free capacity in the structure of a bentonite particle, the faster it accumulates (absorbs) water. The water release rate of bentonite is expressed by the following formula:

$$L(t) = k_r f_d(\theta) S_b \quad (6)$$

Where (k_r) is the release coefficient, day^{-1} , and $f_d(\theta)$ is determined by the following formula:

$$f_d(\theta) = \max \left(0, \frac{\theta_c - \theta}{\theta_c - \theta_{wp}} \right) \quad (7)$$

Where θ_c is the threshold below which the process of active water release begins, and θ_{wp} is the soil moisture. The rate of water release from bentonite depends on soil moisture; that is, when the soil is moist, bentonite releases almost no water. As the soil dries, the release increases. In this case, the mathematical form of this process takes the following expression:

$$Q_b(t) = L(t) - A(t) \quad (8)$$

The maximum water storage in bentonite, calculated per 1 hectare of land, can be defined in terms of the application rate:

$$S_{b,\max} = D_b \cdot w_{\max} \quad (9)$$

Where D_b is the bentonite application rate, kg/m^2 , and w_{\max} is the maximum water absorption, kg of water per kg of dry bentonite. To convert from t/ha , the following formula can be used:

$$D_b = \frac{\text{doze, t/ha} \times 1000}{10000} \quad (10)$$

For example, when applying bentonite to the soil at a rate of 24 t/ha , the bentonite consumption per 1 m^2 is 2.4 kg/m^2 :

$$D_b = \frac{24 \cdot 1000}{10000} = 2.4 \text{ kg/m}^2 \quad (11)$$

Research results showed that applying bentonite to the soil at a rate of 24 t/ha is the optimal value determined through field trials conducted under semi-arid conditions. It was also established that the granules retain 0.8 kg of water per 1 kg of dry material. Therefore:

$$S_{b,\max} = 2.4 \cdot 0.8 = 1.92 \text{ kg/m}^2 \approx 1.92 \text{ mm}$$

If bentonite's water retention is $2\text{--}3 \text{ kg/kg}$, its capacity increases to $4.8\text{--}7.2 \text{ mm}$. This is not a fixed reference value for every specific bentonite but a calculated figure determined experimentally, depending on the chemical-mineralogical composition and structure, individually

for bentonite from each deposit [16–17]. As is well known, the main fertile soil layer in arid lands is located at the very top. For a layer with thickness (z_b), the mass fraction of bentonite application is given by:

$$\beta = \frac{M_b}{M_s} \quad (12)$$

Where (M_b) is the bentonite dose, kg/ha.

$$M_s = 10^4 \cdot z_b \cdot \rho_b$$

Here, ρ_b is the bulk density of the soil, kg/m³.

Example: For $z_b = 0,10$ m and $\rho_b = 1300$ kg/m³, $M_s = 10^4 \cdot 0,10 \cdot 1300 = 1,3 \times 10^6$ kg/ha

When applying bentonite to the soil at a rate of 24 t/ha:

$$\beta = \frac{24000}{1,3 \times 10^6} \approx 0.0185 \quad (13)$$

That is, bentonite will constitute about 1.5% by mass of the soil in the 0–10 cm layer.

Where, AW — available water, mm;

θ_{FC} — moisture at field capacity;

θ_{WP} — soil moisture;

η — fraction of bentonite water actually available to plants.

In this case, the parameter η is needed because not all water retained by bentonite will necessarily be available to roots, which must be determined through experimental field trials [16–18]. In Central Asia, particularly in Uzbekistan, where a sharply continental climate prevails—a type of temperate climate typical of inland continental regions (Eurasia, North America), far from oceans, with extreme temperature fluctuations: very cold and long winters, warm and short summers, and low precipitation—the calculation of the necessary water for rainfed wheat can be performed using a simple seasonal calculation by growth phases [19]. During the autumn–winter period, for moisture accumulation:

$$S_b^{spring} = \min \left(S_{b,max}, \sum A_t - \sum L_t \right) \quad (14)$$

During the spring–summer period, for water consumption:

$$S_b^{summer} = S_b^{spring} - \sum L_t \quad (15)$$

Additional water (moisture) received by the crop:

$$\Delta W_{crop} = \eta \sum L_t \quad (16)$$

Yield increase:

$$\Delta Y = k_y \Delta W_{crop} \quad (17)$$

Where k_y is the crop water-use efficiency coefficient, kg of grain per mm. To conduct actual field experiments in Uzbekistan, it is recommended to evaluate the following experimental parameters in three stages [20]:

Stage One: In laboratory conditions, determine the maximum water absorption (w_{max}), swelling rate (k_a), and water release rate upon drying (k_r) of bentonite granules.

Stage Two: Assess the actual portion of precipitation reaching the bentonite granule layer, how soil moisture changes with depth (0÷10, 10÷20, 20÷40 cm), and the rate of charging/discharging (absorption/release) of water by bentonite granules.

Stage Three: Adjust the mathematical model according to the seasonal dynamics of soil moisture, productive water storage, yield increase, and improvement of key quality characteristics of the crop [21].

To minimize the number of parameters required when constructing the mathematical model, it is sufficient to limit them to:

$S_{b,max}$ – maximum water storage of bentonite, mm;

k_a – water absorption rate;

k_r – water release rate;

θ_c – soil moisture threshold for the onset of active water release;

η – fraction of water available to plants;

β – mass fraction of bentonite in the soil layer.

Then the model can be expressed as follows:

$$\frac{dW}{dt} = I - ET - D - R + L - A \quad (18)$$

$$A = k_a I_b \left(1 - \frac{S_b}{S_{b,max}} \right) \quad (19)$$

$$L = k_r \max \left(0, \frac{\theta_c - \theta}{\theta_c - \theta_{wp}} \right) S_b \quad (20)$$

$$\frac{dS_b}{dt} = A - L \quad (21)$$

The mathematical equations presented above are sufficient for constructing a preliminary conceptual model and obtaining experimental data on the use of bentonite as a water-retaining and water-accumulating element within the soil structure in the rainfed arid lands of Uzbekistan [22–25].

Conclusions.

Thus, to describe the hydrological role of bentonite in rainfed soils, a two-reservoir model was used, in which soil moisture is represented as the sum of matrix soil water and water associated with the bentonite component. The system dynamics are described by water balance equations for the root zone and the kinetics of water absorption/release by bentonite. The soil water retention curve is defined using the van Genuchten function, while the effect of bentonite is accounted for by an additional water retention function parameterized from laboratory data. This approach is consistent with published water retention models for soils and bentonites, as well as with field data showing increased field capacity and available water following bentonite application. The model allows for the preliminary assessment of water accumulation over the autumn–spring period, the duration of moisture retention in the root zone, the maximum water release by bentonite during crop growth, the optimal amount of bentonite to be applied to the soil, the effectiveness of this soil water retention method using bentonite, and the risk assessment of yield loss in dry years, among other applications.

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